

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D3.1 Capacity Building Flagship Programme

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Glossary and Abbreviations

DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
Q&A	Questions and Answers
IoT	Internet of Things
AI	Artificial Intelligence
IP	Intellectual Property
Tech	Technology
Intro	Introduction
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely
VUCA	Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity

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Executive Summary

The Capacity-building flagship programme of the AfriConEU Networking Academy is composed of four sub-programmes, namely:

1. Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach;
2. Capacity building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.);
3. Capacity building on start-up's financial support;
4. Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for
 - i) professionals
 - ii) youth and
 - iii) women.

Each subprogramme is being designed by one or more consortium partners: the [Innovation Technology Cluster](#) (ITC) from Slovenia is designing the first programme, [Porto Business School](#) (PBS) from Portugal is designing the second one, [DPixel](#) from Italy the third one, and lastly, the fourth one is being designed by Porto Business School, [Youthmakers Hub](#) from Greece and the [African Technology Business Network](#) (ATBN) from the United Kingdom.

The goal of this document is to provide an overall description of the sub-programmes. In fact, Deliverable 3.1. Capacity Building Flagship Programme is a document presenting the sub-programmes, the learning objectives, the contents, the tools, the capacity-building methods to be utilised and the expected outcomes. Nevertheless, the tools to deliver the subprogrammes are further detailed in deliverables 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4. Each programme will be composed of a series of activities that are stand-alone but should be understood as part of a complete programme: three (3) workshops, five (5) webinars, two (2) masterclasses and additional resources that will be available on an online repository. Therefore, the Capacity-building flagship programme of the AfriConEU Networking Academy encompasses, in total, 12 workshops, 20 webinars and 8 masterclasses, complemented with additional resources.

This document also includes a chapter regarding the context in which partners explain, from the needs identified in a previous deliverable, which ones are going to be addressed and how, and the ones that are not going to be addressed and why. Indeed, there were two previous tasks, namely Task 2.1: *Local context and needs analysis*, Task 2.2: *Exploration of existing initiatives and good practices for enforcing DIHs*, that are relevant to be mentioned in this document since they served as the basis to choose the adequate themes and methods for the programmes, as well as to identify existing programmes that could be reused in ours.

1. Context

This document is being developed under the work package 3 of the AfriConEU project - AfriConEU Networking Academy. Notwithstanding, there are several inputs from the previous work package useful for the design of the programmes. In fact, deliverable 2.1 *State of play in African DIHs: The case of Ghana, Nigeria, Tanzania and Uganda* identifies needs to be addressed and encompasses important insights on how programmes should be delivered. On the other side, deliverable 2.2 *Online database with DIHs Capacity Building programmes* gathers several existing programmes that can be reused in this programme. Moreover, deliverable 2.3. *Lessons from existing initiatives and good practices for enforcing DIHs capacities* presents relevant insights to deliver the programmes.

According to D.2.1, African Digital Innovation Hubs are facing several challenges, namely:

1. Lack of core funding, limiting the ability of hubs to invest in their own capacities and infrastructure.
2. Lack of funding for medium/long-term programmes (much of the funding that hubs receive is for short-term programmes).
3. Lack of sustainable business models and more diversified and sustainable revenue streams.
4. Lack of in-depth business development expertise in key areas like marketing, design thinking, market research and user testing (which are necessary for developing successful business from idea to scale).
5. Lack of capacity in facilitating investment and lack of fundraising skills and capacity, limiting the financial resources of hubs.
6. Lack of knowledge in gender-related issues.
7. Lack of development of effective ecosystem-wide partnerships, namely hub-government, hub-business, hub-investor, hub-hub, strengthening its networks.
8. Lack of data to back up the recommendations that hubs are making to governments to support better policymaking.
9. Lack of knowledge to invest in startups and develop commercially viable relationships with investors.
10. Lack of a standardized offer.

Therefore, capacity-building programmes should follow some recommendations such as:

- A. Capacity building programmes should focus on clear outcomes and tangible outputs.
- B. Peer to peer learning should form a key component of hub capacity building programmes (e.g. providing joint capacity building activities which bring together hubs from across the different African ecosystems).
- C. Short sprints spread out over a longer period of time can help to provide the flexibility needed by hub leaders.
- D. Capacity building programmes should target both hub leaders as well as their teams.
- E. Capacity building programmes should be co-created together with hub leaders and provide a sense of ownership. Given the diverse contexts and capacities of hubs, further consultation should be done to further adapt content to meet specific hubs needs.
- F. Capacity building programmes should be complemented by funding to enable concrete implementation of recommendations and learning outcomes (e.g. developing a joint grant or corporate sponsorship proposal)
- G. Face to face interaction is essential.

The following part of the document will, then, state which of the following needs and recommendations are addressed and how, or, on the other side, the ones not addressed and why.

Table 1 - DIHs' needs addressed through the programmes

Need/ Recommendation	Addressed	How/why
1, 2, 5	Yes	Through the capacity building on start-up's financial support, DIH will gain knowledge on financial issues and access to funding.
3	Yes	Through the capacity building in business development models and multi actor approach, DIH will acquire skills in business models.
4	Yes	Through the capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women,

		particularly through the marketing part of the programme, DIH will learn about the referred needs.
6	Yes	Through the capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly through the gender-lens part of the programme, the issue of gender-responsive programmes will be addressed.
7	Yes	Through the capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly through the “Collaborate to innovate” part.
8	Yes	Through the capacity building in technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.), DIH will learn new insights on data important to solve this challenge.
9	No	This need will not be directly addressed. However, support in finance-related issues will be provided through the capacity building on start-up’s financial support.
10	No	No tools will be given for DIH to present a standardised offer. It is up to them to address this problem.
A	Yes	Clear objectives will be presented at the beginning of the programmes and tangible outcomes will be required during the activities.
B	Yes	Peer discussion and feedback will be stimulated.
C	Yes	The programme is designed as stand-alone activities despite they belong to an overall programme. Hence, each participant can choose its own pace according to the needs and availability.

D	Yes	Programmes are mainly targeted to DIH managers but all colleagues are welcome.
E	No	The programmes were not jointly designed with their audience. Nevertheless, they are open and flexible so new insights will be taken into consideration. Besides, existing content will be reused and adapted, also including content suggested by the participants.
F	No	No funding will be provided.
G	Yes	Face to face interaction is foreseen.

Furthermore, D2.3. presents some relevant insights on DIHs needs that will be addressed such as:

- DIHs need additional knowledge on networking, strategy and business development.
- DIHs need guidance on service portfolio, as well as on communication and awareness creation.
- DIH prefer online shorter programmes.
- DIH aim to participate in more interactive programmes.

For the development of the programmes, the goal is to use tools, training contents and resources already developed in other capacity-building programmes – the intention is to reuse and re-adapt training resources and develop standardised capacity building material, rather than content development.

Consequently, PowerPoint presentations and other material specifically developed for the programmes' purpose will be freely available in the online repository. Additionally, existing materials will be used to deliver the activities. D2.2 contains an extensive list of existing materials, which will be presented to the trainers for them to prepare the sessions with these resources in mind.

Some examples can be found below:

Table 2 - Existing material used in the programmes

Existing material	Programme in which will be used
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LjvYsL3Gv_E&ab_channel=I.Team	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Collaborate to innovate” part.
https://smartfactories.eu/uploads/7b848e7ce7c6a2a9222acbfa4a18577a3fcd7019.xlsx	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Purpose-driven DIH” part.
https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/library/reports-resources/Presentations/2020-0131-SAH-how-to-develop-a-DIH_M-Butter-1580481436.pdf	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Purpose-driven DIH” part.
https://youtu.be/KglUBKiqvuE	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Purpose-driven DIH” part.
https://spaces.fundingbox.com/spaces/dih-net-eu-digital-	Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women, particularly in the “Collaborate to innovate” part.
https://dihworld.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Webinar-20-July_PwC_v1.0-1.pdf	Capacity building in technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.),
https://smartagrihubs.curatr3.com/courses/dih-exchange/home#level/232328	Capacity building in business development models and multi actor approach
https://sellalab.com/innovation-financer/	Capacity building on start-up’s financial support (Backend material will support the financial programme, especially in terms of exploring finance ecosystems and lifecycles)

https://www.britishcouncil.ro/sites/default/files/creative_hubkit_en.pdf	Capacity building on start-up's financial support; Capacity building in business development models and multi actor approach
https://www.afrilabs-capacity.com/resources/downloads/all	Capacity building on start-up's financial support
https://smetraktion.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/FinanceToolkit_financial_April2019.pdf	Capacity building on start-up's financial support

2. Programme 1: Capacity building in business development models and multi-actor approach

Main AfriConEU Partner Responsible: [Innovation Technology Cluster](#) (ITC), Slovenia.

Learning objectives

The objective of this subprogramme is to understand the multi-sidedness and indirectness of the DIH business model and its service portfolio. The business model should be configured according to the overall strategic vision and should also encompass that the multi-actor approach is essential in DIHs functioning.

Overall, this subprogramme aims to support DIHs in setting up their strategy and designing their business model (as this two are interconnected). By the end of this Subprogramme, DIH will be able to:

- Understand the importance of DIH strategy development and implementation.
- Correlate DIHs' vision and objectives with the DIH Strategy and draft a preliminary strategy for DIH.
- Linking Strategy and Business Modelling.
- Understand the importance of Business Modelling for DIHs and the path to sustainability.
- Learn how a DIH can define its Business Model based on the offered service portfolio.
- Draft a preliminary Business Model for DIH.

Contents

Digital Innovation hubs (DIHs) are one-stop-shops that support different stakeholders in a multi-actor approach in their digital transformation, offering them various services.

A business strategy defines why the company exists and focuses on stakeholders eager for solutions, a value proposition, an inventory of the resources and

capabilities needed to deliver that value, and an effective business model consistently providing that value. Strategy is the goal, where the company should go, and the business model is the company's path. A business model and a business strategy are two essential pre-conditions and fundamentals of an organisation's existence.

The challenge for DIHs is to build a sustainable business model around their services. As stated in Deliverable 2.1. *State of play in African DIHs*, many hubs lack sustainable business models and are financially vulnerable because they rely on grants. However, DIHs should think from the outset about how they will combine the different service lines and revenue streams in a financially viable way. Furthermore, the DIHs can have different business models: base funding from local, regional or national funds or private funding, such as membership fees.

In the context of this subprogramme, the participant will have the opportunity to relate DIHs Strategic vision with the theory and understand the business modelling and its relationship with the strategy.

Tools

Webinars:

- DIH Strategy and Strategy Resources
- DIH Business Models
- The Business Model Navigator
- Building a Business Plan
- Sustainability in DIHs

Workshops:

- Tailor-made strategies for DIH
- Business Model Canvas Template and Instructions
- Lean Canvas Template and Instructions

Masterclasses:

- Case study of successful DIHs (2 parts)

Capacity building methods

Webinars will be online lectures with practical cases. In workshops, practical tools will be demonstrated, which participants can use on their own.

For the online repository, articles, books and other interesting publications will be selected and published on the AfriConEU web page.

In masterclasses, successful DIH will be showcased as exemplary practices and good practices for transferring.

Expected outcomes

Lean Canvas or Business Model Canvas for participants' DIH. Templates will be available.

3. Programme 2: Capacity Building in Technology transfer of innovative technologies (IoT, AI, Big data, etc.)

Main AfriConEU Partner Responsible: Porto Business School (PBS), Portugal.

Learning objectives

This sub-programme aims at helping DIHs in providing technological expertise and experimentation facilities. It covers IP management, the specificities of creating a technology-based start-up, economic valorisation of technologies and their transfer to market, data-driven innovation, and business intelligence and analytics.

At the end, participants will be able to:

- Formulate an action plan to transfer a technology (IP) from lab to market.
- Get a comprehensive overview of the technology transfer process.
- Know the fundamentals of technology identification, assessment, protection and maturation.
- Understand the entrepreneurial journey of a technology-based start-up.
- Apply data-driven decision making and problem-solving skills.
- Master the concepts of data mining, data analytics, quality of data, management systems, and business intelligence.

Contents

This programme encompasses several themes essential to promote the technological knowledge of DIH managers to help companies and startups in tech processes.

The programme begins with an overview of the start-up creation from the innovative technologies process, followed by data-driven innovation.

The technology transfer process is, subsequently, fully addressed from the concept to the stages, including the motivations and benefits.

Then, business intelligence and analytics are delivered for participants to understand the business side of a data-driven world.

The technology valorisation process is also exploited with the technology identification phase, the technology assessment phase, the value proposition of the technology, pathways to transfer technology, development and proof of concept, and other topics.

The market uptake process is addressed in a very comprehensive way, encompassing several crucial phases and steps to pursue the technologies' entrance into the market.

Finally, the IP issues are approached.

Tools

Workshops

- The Technology Transfer Process
- The Technology Valorization Process
- The Market Uptake Process

Webinars

- Navigating through the Intellectual Property maze
- Leverage start-up creation from innovative technologies
- Fast-tracking technologies to market
- Data-driven innovation
- Business Intelligence and Analytics

Masterclasses

- Lessons from European startups
- Business Intelligence and Analytics

Capacity building methods

- Case Studies.
- The Technology Transfer Canvas.
- Invention Disclosure Forms.
- Conversation with Researchers to Identify Inventions.
- Information Available to Identify Inventions.
- Technology Assessment Dashboard.

- Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs).

Expected outcomes

- Action Plan to transfer technology.
- Technology Brochures.
- Technology Assessment Dashboards.

4. Programme 3: Capacity building on start-up's financial support

Main AfriConEU Partner Responsible: DPixel, Italy.

Learning objectives

This sub-programme is aimed at building participant skills regarding several financial areas. This includes understanding various sources of financing and how to use and access them. It also includes principles of financial management and revenue streams. Participants will understand both how to apply these topics in their own work and to coach startups in them.

By the end of this Programme's content, participants will be able to:

- Propose, plan and identify appropriate funding instruments for various points along an entrepreneurial lifecycle.
- Differentiate between the uses, benefits and drawbacks of the major sources of traditional and alternative innovation finance.
- Develop an appropriate and durable financial model, for costs, revenue, and funding needs, using bootstrapping or outside financing.
- Perform appropriate financial controls and produce documentation to support modelling, management, and seeking finances.
- Build relationships with funding sources of various types by identifying their needs and interests and preparing appropriate presentations, programs, and documentation.
- Apply all of the above skills both in the context of the management of a digital innovation hub and in the context of training and supporting startups backed by the hub.

Contents

The material for this programme will cover six primary themes:

- A. Traditional investment instruments such as pre-seed and seed funding, angels, VCs, series funding, and exits.

- B. Alternative financial instruments such as impact investing, crowdfunding, subsidized finance, and microcredit, particularly in the context of Sub-Saharan Africa.
- C. Durable sources of funding for DIHs with a focus on bootstrapping through operational revenue streams and connections which will provide an ongoing source of income through incubation and acceleration programs.
- D. Financial management including controlling costs and financial documentation and projections with a focus on securing financial support.
- E. Mapping of financial actors, identifying and approaching potential sources of funding available within a specific ecosystem and the key role played by DIHs.
- F. Preparation of projects (both startups and hubs) for investment and investor relationships.

Tools

Masterclasses:

- Essentials of Innovation Finance
- Financing Digital Innovation Hubs

Webinars:

- Durable Funding Sources for DIHs
- Phases of Investment
- Crowdfunding and Microcredit
- Impact Investing and Subsidized Finance
- Valuations of Projects, Financial Management, Projections

Workshops:

- Bootstrapping, Revenue Models and Managerial Accounting
- Preparing for Investment and Investor Relationships
- Building and Using a Network of Funding Sources

Capacity building methods

- Seminar-style lectures.
- Best practices.
- Hands-on use of draft or example content.
- Live collaborative exercises.
- Peer to peer knowledge sharing and group work.

Expected outcomes

By the end of the material presented above, participants will have developed or have the skills to develop the following:

- A comprehensive mapping of financing sources available within their ecosystem, and current gaps in those sources.
- A sustainable business model and financing plan for their hub.
- Financial and non-financial KPIs and other reporting for their operations, along with reasonable projections for the future.
- Pitching and promotional material that will help them in approaching funding sources and other partners.
- Financial and operational plans and projections for projects supported by the hub.
- Advice to project owners regarding which funding streams are appropriate for their needs, how to approach them and how to use their funding.
- Plans for relationships with financial and other actors in their ecosystem, which will in turn support revenue streams and opportunities for startups.

5. Programme 4: Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women

Main AfriConEU Partner Responsible: Porto Business School (PBS), Portugal; Youthmakers Hub (YMH), Greece; and African Technology Business Network (ATBN), United Kingdom.

Learning objectives

The programme Capacity building in digital and entrepreneurial skills development for i) professionals, ii) youth and iii) women includes 5 sub-chapters with different learning objectives:

1. Gender Lens Innovation
 - a. Understand systemic drivers of gender inequality and how to build more gender-inclusive innovation ecosystems.
 - b. Apply gender-lens design to develop gender-inclusive interventions/programs.
 - c. Understand how capital allocation contributes to gender inequality and the emerging tools and approaches in gender lens finance.
2. Digital Marketing for Successful Businesses
 - a. Learn digital marketing tools.
 - b. Learn basic concepts about digital marketing.
 - c. Learn basic concepts about digital marketing plan.
 - d. Identify challenges of digital marketing.
3. Purpose-driven Digital Innovation Hubs
 - a. Understand what is purpose-driven innovation, as well as a purpose-driven strategy and how it can be employed in a DIH.
 - b. Set the scene for their own DIH.
 - c. Know the ecosystem of African DIHs, particularly the key challenges they face and how to overcome them.
 - d. Learn the basic concepts of project management and strategic planning.
 - e. Understand the importance of human-centred approaches through organisational culture, future of work and leadership.
 - f. Learn how to manage change and harness growth opportunities.
4. Impact assessment

- a. Understand why measuring impact is important and where and when it can help you work.
 - b. Gain familiarity with several impact measurement methodologies.
 - c. Explain trends in the impact measurement space.
 - d. Build Theory of Change.
 - e. Ask critical questions about impact measurement.
5. Collaborate to innovate:
- a. Learn new organisational practices to manage innovation ecosystems.
 - b. Understand how to leverage key stakeholders within innovation ecosystems (entrepreneurs, universities, risk capital providers, government, and large corporations) and engage them in the most suitable way.

Contents

1. Gender Lens Innovation

In this subchapter, participants shall be introduced to gender lens thinking and tools. The goal is to help hub leaders build programs that contribute to promoting gender inclusion within their innovation ecosystem. Specifically, we will look at how to market programmes to the female audience, how to design programs around the unique needs of women and how to get access to relevant kinds of funding.

Themes to be discussed include:

- Gender lens innovation – Building inclusive ecosystems

Under this theme, participants will be guided first, to examine the drivers of gender inequality within their innovation ecosystems. Second, to understand how current structures and practices may contribute towards gender inequalities. And lastly, how these structures and practices can be challenged to promote gender inclusion. This theme will be delivered via a webinar.

- Gender lens Design – Designing inclusive programs

Under this theme, participants will be introduced to gender-lens innovation including an introduction to human-centred design and applying a gender lens to human-centred design.

This theme will be delivered as a hands on workshop in which participants will carry out a [gender assessment](#) of their own work in order to identify gender barriers as well as apply to knowledge acquired to design interventions and

programmes that promote gender inclusion.

- Gender lens finance – Bridging the gender financing gap

In this theme, participants will be introduced to the Gender Lens Investment landscape including key actors, emerging tools and approaches. They will also gain a deeper understanding of where the opportunities for gender lens investing lie and how to better support women entrepreneurs in their programmes to access funding. This theme will be delivered as a masterclass including talks by gender lens investors and experts.

2. Digital Marketing for Successful Businesses

The subchapter Digital Marketing for Successful Businesses includes several topics, which will be delivered through different tools.

The first topic is the basic Digital Marketing principles so the participants can understand better how it works, what is included in Digital Marketing, so it is easier for them to implement it in their businesses. The second topic is about digital marketing plan and learn how to structure it better, what to include and how to adapt it in their working environment. The third topic is about learning digital marketing tools that can support their businesses and learn in practice how to use them and identify which tools work better for their businesses.

These topics will be addressed through workshops and interactive webinars.

3. Purpose-driven DIH

The subchapter Purpose-driven Digital Innovation Hubs is composed of diverse themes, which will be delivered through different tools.

The first theme is the Digital Innovation Hub itself in the sense that it is essential to define the identity and activity of the DIH to define a strategy. Therefore, the first contents covered are the purpose, the role and the processes of the DIH – setting the scene -, as well as key business challenges, project management and strategic planning – DIH activity.

These contents will be addressed through one hands-on workshop in which participants will define their DIHs and outline an overall action plan addressing key challenges faced by African DIH based on the results of WP2.

After defining the purpose of the DIH, participants are invited to understand the purpose-driven innovation theme through a webinar addressing purpose-driven innovation, managing change and growth opportunities.

These themes will be further complemented through additional materials upload on the project's website, not only focusing on DIH and purpose-driven innovation, but also focusing on the people's side – human-centered innovation. It is important that DIH leaders are aware of leadership and people management principals, as well as the future skills the market will demand.

4. Impact assessment

Every business, program, or initiative has (positive or negative) impact on society and on the environment. Knowing how to measure this impact allows managers, investors, policy makers and implementers to make informed and better decisions to enhance and strengthen those programs that improve lives, or to modify or reassign resources of those programs which are not achieving their objectives.

This sub-chapter offers a unique opportunity to learn tools and apply impact management and measurement. Participants will gain an introductory outlook of impact management, including measurement, monitoring and evaluation of social programs and initiatives. After the session, hub leaders will be able to understand why measuring impact is relevant, understand impact language, and gain familiarity with relevant tools of impact measurement. These topics will be addressed through a webinar and a masterclass.

5. Collaborate to innovate

This part will focus on strategies to collaborate, the benefits of collaboration and platforms that support collaboration. Particular importance will be given to startups-corporates collaboration in order to engage young professionals in the innovation process.

Tools

Workshops

1. Gender lens innovation
2. Digital marketing for successful businesses
3. Purpose-driven DIH (focused on the "Setting the scene for DIH" and "DIH activity")

Webinars

1. Gender lens innovation
2. Bridging the gap between offline and online marketing
3. Purpose-driven DIH (focused on the Purpose-driven innovation)

4. Impact Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning
5. Collaborate to Innovate

Masterclasses

1. Gender-lens finance – Bridging the gender finance gap
2. Building a Theory of Change

Capacity building methods

- Lecture—Showing/Telling.
- Video-Based Learning (VBL).
- Contact with experts.
- Discussion-Based Learning.
- Peer feedback.
- Case-based Exercises / Case studies.
- Challenge-Based Learning.
- Hands-on work.

Expected outcomes

Participants will gain insights, strategies and tools to think more creatively and holistically about Digital Innovation Hubs, being able to:

1. Gender Lens Innovation
 - Identify and understand the drivers of gender barriers within their innovation ecosystems
 - Understand gender-lens design tools and approaches
 - Design an intervention/programme to promote gender inclusion
 - Better position and promote their programmes to reach more women participants.
 - Gain a basic understanding of the gender-lens finance landscape, and approaches
 - Better support women entrepreneurs to access finance.
2. Digital Marketing for Successful Businesses
 - Improve digital marketing skills.
 - Identify digital marketing tools.
 - Design a digital marketing plan.
 - Outline key digital marketing challenges.

3. Purpose-driven DIH

- Define their DIH purpose and role to better communicate it outdoors.
- Identify their core processes and how to perform them more effectively.
- Outline the key business challenges African DIHs face.
- Understand the basic concepts of project management.
- Design a strategic plan.
- Understand the meaning of a purpose-driven strategy and how it can be employed in a DIH.
- Comprehend the meaning for a human-centered approach.

4. Impact assessment

- Understand basic concepts of impact measurement
- Design an impact measurement strategy for their DIH
- Build a Theory of Change

5. Collaborate to innovate

- Develop new organisational practices.
- Learn how to manage innovation ecosystems.
- Acquire strategies to engage key stakeholders within innovation ecosystems (entrepreneurs, universities, risk capital providers, government, and large corporations).

6. Workflow

The sub-programmes and activities, although stand-alone, belong to a single programme: Capacity Building Flagship Programme.

This part of the document aims, therefore, to design a workflow that describes the journey a participant should follow if one aims to perform all the activities.

The Capacity Building Flagship Programme is composed by 12 workshops, 20 webinars, 8 Masterclasses, whose workflow can be found below. Besides, additional material useful to enrich the knowledge of participants will be freely available at the online repository (<https://africoneu.eu/training-resources/>). This material will be based on previous capacity-building programmes according to the deliverable D2.2, as well as further data suggested by the consortium partners, the lecturers of the activities and the participants.

Table 3 - Capacity Building Flagship Programme Tools

Workshop	Purpose-driven DIH
Webinar	DIH strategy and strategy resources
Masterclass	Case study of successful DIHs
Workshop	DIH strategy and strategy resources
Webinar	Purpose-driven DIH
Webinar	Gender lens innovation – Building inclusive ecosystems
Workshop	Gender lens innovation
Masterclass	Gender lens finance
Webinar	Collaborate to innovate
Webinar	DIH Business Model
Workshop	DIH Business Model
Masterclass	Case study of successful DIHs
Webinar	The Business Model Navigator
Webinar	Durable funding sources for digital innovation hubs
Masterclass	Essentials of Innovation Finance
Webinar	Phases of investment
Workshop	Draft a Preliminary Business Model for your DIHs

Webinar	Building a Business Plan
Workshop	Bootstrapping, Revenue Models and Managerial Accounting
Webinar	Crowdfunding and microcredit
Webinar	Impact investing and subsidised finance
Workshop	Preparing projects for investment and investor relationships
Masterclass	Financing Digital Innovation Hubs
Webinar	Valuations of projects, financial management and projections
Workshop	Building and using a network of funding sources
Webinar	Leverage start-up creation from innovative technologies
Masterclass	Lessons from European start-ups
Webinar	Impact Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning
Masterclass	Building a Theory of Change
Webinar	Data-driven innovation
Workshop	The Technology Transfer Process
Webinar	Business Intelligence and Analytics
Masterclass	Business Intelligence and Analytics
Workshop	The Technology Valorisation Process
Webinar	Fast-tracking technologies to market
Workshop	The Market Uptake Process
Webinar	Navigating through the Intellectual Property maze
Webinar	Bridging the Gap between Offline and Online Marketing
Workshop	Digital Marketing for Successful Businesses
Webinar	Digital Innovation Hubs Sustainability

7. Conclusion

The Capacity Building Flagship Programme of the AfriConEU Academy aims to raise the capacities of African DIHs in serving in the best way their own needs and long-term sustainability, as well as the needs of local SMEs, start-ups and young people with an emphasis to women and people from marginalized backgrounds. This document presents the learning objectives and the sub-programmes included, the capacity-building methods to be utilised and the expected outcomes. The programme is composed of 4 subprogrammes in different areas to answer to different needs identified.

Each subprogramme will be delivered through a series of webinars, workshops, masterclasses and additional materials such as videos, case studies, readings, etc. Nevertheless, these stand-alone activities must be perceived as a whole programme, so it was essential to design all the programmes before implementation in order to keep them aligned and similarly structured. In fact, there is a rationale behind the choice of topics, which is explained in the “context” chapter.

This document should be perceived as open and flexible, enabling the adaptation of the content and format by the implementing trainers. Trainers may change some of the content, provided the overall structure is preserved.

It is crucial to analyse this document together with D3.2, D3.3, D3.4 and D3.5 as they encompass the structure of the tools used to deliver the programmes (workshops, webinars, online repository and masterclasses, respectively).